

Prevalence of Breast Cancer in Northern Area of Pakistan

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Breast cancer was identified to be a malignant tumor that develops from cells of the breast. Breast cancer is also the primary cause of cancer death among women globally, causing approximately 375,000 deaths every year. A total of 85 persons took part in the survey and provided their views about breast cancer. 80% of the students / faculty of Hazara University were “aware” of breast cancer. 9.4% of individual surveyed had one of their parents suffering from cancer. 15.2% individual believed that the breast cancer can occur in both male and female. Majority of the individuals (81.2%) believed that breast cancer can occur only in female. 12.9% individual believed that breast cancer is restricted to occur in older ages. Almost half of the individual surveyed (47.1%) believed that breast cancer is caused by smoking and drugs. Similarly, half (49.4%) of the individuals know about symptoms of breast cancer. 29.6% individuals know about mammography diagnosis of the disease. Regarding treatment of breast cancer, 56.5% individuals had some idea about treatment while 43.5% individuals did not know about treatment of breast cancer. Present study revealed that although educated still enough awareness is lacking among the participants exposing them to high risks of the cancer.

Keywords: BREAST CANCER, HEALTH AWARENESS, CANCER IN NORTHERN AREAS, HEALTH CARE.

Introduction

Cancer origin is accredited to the Greek physician Hippocrates¹, who was deliberated “Father of Medicine”. Hippocrates used the words carcinoses and carcinoma² to Breast cancer is a malignant tumor that develops from cells of the breast.³ Cancer is a disease that result from the changes in the cellular behavior due to changes in the genetic material of the cells; as a result, cancer cause proliferates in uncontrolled manner forming malignant tumor that tend to grow in an invasive manner, destroying the normal tissue in which they appear.⁴ There are approximately fifteen forms of breast cancer. Statistically, 99% of people who develop breast cancer are female. Most breast disorders are benign⁵ (not cancerous). Benign breast tumors do not spread outside of the breast and are not life threatening. Other tumors are malignant (cancerous) and may become life threatening. Benign tumors, such as papilloma and fibroadenoma are common in women⁶ but are extremely rare in men. All breast cancer starts in the ducts or lobules.

The prevalence of breast cancer in recent years has prompted women⁷ to seek medical advice randomly with minimal breast symptoms, but only a small number of women are aware of the proper methods of conducting breast self-examination (BSE)⁸ or the importance of radiological screening for breast cancer. The risk factors most closely associated with breast cancer are age, personal and family history, and reproductive history. Other personal factors such as obesity, a high-fat diet, and alcohol intake have also been suspected. In the Middle East, the incidence of breast cancer is rising and affecting a younger population compared to the West⁹. Breast cancer is increased in women before the last 30 years. In the United States and Canada with women born after 1920 having lower breast cancer death rates than women born earlier¹⁰. Breast cancer death rates fell about 10% between 1989 and 1993 in England and Wales. The age-adjusted breast cancer mortality rate for white females in the United States dropped 6.8% from 1989 to 1993.¹¹

¹ Koutsiaris, E., et al. "UP-01.090 A Historical Approach to the Causes of Cancer." *Urology* 78.3 (2011): S215.

² Sudhakar, Akulapalli. "History of cancer, ancient and modern treatment methods." *Journal of cancer science & therapy* 1.2 (2009): 1.

³ Al-Hajj, Muhammad, et al. "Prospective identification of tumorigenic breast cancer cells." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 100.7 (2003): 3983-3988.

⁴ Ruddon, Raymond W. *Cancer biology*. Oxford University Press, 2007.

⁵ Guray, Merih, and Aysegul A. Sahin. "Benign breast diseases: classification, diagnosis, and management." *The oncologist* 11.5 (2006): 435-449.

⁶ Cummings, Margaret C., et al. "Fibroadenoma and intraduct papilloma—a common pathogenesis?." *Virchows Archiv* 455.3 (2009): 271-275.

⁷ Burk, Larry, DelMarie Wehner, and Mary Scott Soo. "Dreams Prior to Biopsy for Suspected Breast Cancer: A Preliminary Survey." *EXPLORE* (2020).

⁸ Galary, Kawther Mahmood, Rebar Yahya Abdullah, and Robar Anwar Majid. "Practicing Breast Self-Examination Related Knowledge among Women at General Hospitals in Duhok City." *Mosul Journal of Nursing* 8.1 (2020): 97-105.

⁹ AL-FUADI, A., and DM PARKIN. "CANCER IN IRAQ: SEVEN-YEAR DATA FROM THE BAGHDAD." *Cancer Prevention in Developing Countries: Proceedings of the 2nd UICC Conference on Cancer Prevention*. Pergamon, 1986.

¹⁰ Mettlin, Curtis. "Global breast cancer mortality statistics." *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians* 49.3 (1999): 138-144.

¹¹ Kinsey, Tracy, et al. "Secular trends in mortality from common cancers in the United States by educational attainment, 1993–2001." *Journal of the National Cancer Institute* 100.14 (2008): 1003-1012.

Most of the research into the causes of breast cancer has focused on identifying the genes that make a small percentage of women more susceptible to breast cancer.¹² A wide range of rates for the prevalence of sexual problems in breast cancer survivors have been reported. Among recent studies, rates range from a low of 15% for reduced physiological arousal to a high of 64% for reduced sexual desire. Breast cancer is second only to lung cancer as a cause of cancer deaths in American women. More than 200,000 American women are diagnosed annually with breast cancer. Nearly 40,000 women die annually of breast cancer. Alcohol and tobacco are risk factors for breast cancer has been systematically studied by the Collaborative Group on Hormonal Factors in Breast Cancer¹³ when a cure is most likely. Age at menarche, age at first pregnancy, nulliparity, and age at menopause are established risk factors for breast cancer.¹⁴ Most of these factors show a modest relative risk of 1.5 to 3.5, and even when considered together, they may not be adequate for screening individuals.¹⁵ Although it has been demonstrated, that mutation of *p53*, *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes can lead to increased breast cancer risk. These mutations are present in far less than 1% of the general population.¹⁶ Pregnancy also increases the risk of breast cancer developing in carriers of *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* mutations.¹⁷ Carriers of these mutations who have children are significantly more likely to develop breast cancer by the age of 40 years than carriers who are nulliparous, and each pregnancy is associated with an increased risk of cancer.¹⁸ Breast cancer can be detected by three components that are breast self-examination, a clinical breast examination, and mammography. The treatment of breast cancer is involved chemotherapy, radiation, hormonal therapy, or bone marrow transplant. These treatments may be used alone or in combination.¹⁹

Pakistan is a developing country and rural areas are home to most of the population. No organized health infrastructure for the rural population is required in rural areas of Pakistan. Illiteracy in women is also a significant cause of breast cancer because women are ignorant of personal hygiene conditions. Because of gender-based violence, most Pakistani women have no adequate access to medical services. Women comprise more than half of the population. Among women in Pakistan, sexually transmitted diseases and breast cancer have become very common diseases. Socio-economic problems in rural areas of Pakistan are responsible for the declining health of women. At some stage of life, 1 in 9 Pakistani women has become the

¹² Oldenburg, Rogier A., et al. "Genetic susceptibility for breast cancer: how many more genes to be found?." *Critical reviews in oncology/hematology* 63.2 (2007): 125-149.

¹³ Escala-Garcia, Maria, et al. "Breast cancer risk factors and their effects on survival: a Mendelian randomisation study." *BMC medicine* 18.1 (2020): 1-10.

¹⁴ Chen, Hongjie, et al. "Interactions Between Mammographic Density Phenotypes and Established Risk Factors on Breast Cancer Risk, by Tumor Subtype and Menopausal Status." *American Journal of Epidemiology* (2020).

¹⁵ Wong, Katy, et al. "Mortality studies in psoriatic arthritis. Results from a single outpatient clinic. I. Causes and risk of death." *Arthritis & Rheumatism* 40.10 (1997): 1868-1872.

¹⁶ Ford, Deborah, et al. "Genetic heterogeneity and penetrance analysis of the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes in breast cancer families." *The American Journal of Human Genetics* 62.3 (1998): 676-689.

¹⁷ Trägårdh, Gun, and Dan Johansson. "Purification of alkaline cleaning solutions from the dairy industry using membrane separation technology." *Desalination* 119.1-3 (1998): 21-29.

¹⁸ Jernström, Helena, et al. "Pregnancy and risk of early breast cancer in carriers of *BRCA1* and *BRCA2*." *The Lancet* 354.9193 (1999): 1846-1850.

¹⁹ Miller, Kimberly D., et al. "Cancer treatment and survivorship statistics, 2019." *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians* 69.5 (2019): 363-385.

patient of breast cancer.²⁰

As far as the non-communicable diseases are concerned in Pakistan, cancer is the leading cause of death. To-date, no study from Pakistan has reported age-standardized and cancer-specific incidence and mortality rates among men and women.²¹ The absence of a national cancer registry complicates the situation further. Thus, there are no national figures or data on incidence or prevalence of different cancers in the country. Various studies which have been published on cancer incidence or prevalence in Pakistan provide regional data that is often variable due to the peculiar ethnic composition of that specific region or area.

Source: *Cancer Country Profile - World Health Organization*²²

²⁰ Baig, Mehreen, et al. "Factors influencing delayed presentation of breast cancer at a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan." *Cancer Reports* 2.1 (2019): e1141.

²¹ Sarwar, Muhammad Rehan, and Anum Saqib. "Cancer prevalence, incidence and mortality rates in Pakistan in 2012." *Cogent Medicine* 4.1 (2017): 1288773.

²² Cancer Country Profile - World Health Organization, <https://gco.iarc.fr/today/data/factsheets/populations/586-pakistan-factsheets.pdf>

Number of new cases in 2020, females, all ages

Source: Pakistan | CancerIndex²³

Materials and methods

AREA OF STUDY

Prevalence of breast cancer in Northern area was a survey type of research so conducted the two districts of Hazara division Mansehra and Abbottabad. In Abbottabad, data collected from cancer hospital INOR (Institute of nuclear medicines oncology and radiotherapy). In Mansehra survey was conducted in Hazara University, employees and students.

Questionnaire

Following questionnaire was developed during present research to obtain information about awareness of breast cancer in Hazara division. A total of 120 questionnaire were distributed, 85 responses were received. Out of 85 samples 80 samples were from female, and 5 from male individual.

Result and Discussion

A survey was conducted to determine the awareness of breast cancer in Northern area of breast cancer. Students and faculty of seven academic departments of Hazara University were surveyed. These students belonged to different cities and villages of Northern areas. The different departments included in the study were, Department of Genetics, Microbiology, Botany, Biochemistry, English, Chemistry, English and Law.

²³ Pakistan | CancerIndex , <http://www.cancerindex.org/Pakistan>
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A total of 120 questionnaires were distributed, 85 responses were received. Among total of 85 individuals 80 were female and 5 were male. The Questionnaire was divided into five parts which contained General questions, Specific questions, Family history, Knowledge questions, and Awareness questions. A total of 36 questions were included in the survey.

Regarding the topic of breast cancer 80% of the participants were “aware” of the breast cancer. The awareness rate for respondents from various departments surveyed was, 95% for Genetics, 80% for Biochemistry, 70% for Law, 75% for Chemistry, 60% for Microbiology, 50% for English. The reason for high level of awareness in the Genetics department was that the respondents had already the critical background about the subject. On the other hand, only 45% of English students were aware of the breast cancer because these students in general had no clear idea of the disease as part of their curriculum.

9.4% of individual surveyed had one of their parents suffering from cancer (Fig 1), while 90.6% individual had no known history of cancer in their percents. Only 15.2% individual believed that the breast cancer can occur in both male and female (Fig 2). Majority of the individuals (81.2%) believed that breast cancer can occur only in female. Only (12.9%) individual believed that breast cancer is restricted to occur in older ages (Fig 3). Almost half of the individual surveyed (47.1) believed that breast cancer is caused by smoking and drugs (Figs 4,5). Similarly, half (49.4%) of the individuals know about symptoms of breast cancer (Fig 6). Only 29.6% individuals know about mammography diagnosis of the disease (Fig 7). Regarding treatment of breast cancer, 56.5% individuals had some idea about treatment while 43.5% individuals did not know about treatment of breast cancer (Fig 8).

Data regarding frequency distribution of various kinds of cancer (Data collected from Institute of Nuclear Medicine Oncology & Radiotherapy INOR Abbottabad) revealed that breast cancer has the highest rate of occurrence among various kinds of cancer patients in Hazara Division during 2005, 2006 & 2007 (Tables 1-3, Figs 9-11). In 2008 skin cancer rate was highest (15.5%) followed by breast cancer (11.2%).

Present study revealed that though a reasonably larger part of population knows about breast cancer, living also consolation to the increasing rate of incidence of breast cancer, it is important to organize such kind of surveys on a larger scale. Information obtains from such surveys will help device latter strategies to fight the disease.

1 = Individual with parents having cancer
 2 = Individuals with parents have not cancer/don't know

Figure 1: Pie Chart representing family history of breast cancer survey conducted

1 = Individuals believes breast cancer can occur in both male and female
 2 = Individuals having no idea about gender breast cancer occurrence of breast cancer
 3 = Individuals believe that breast cancer can occur in female only

Figure 2: Awareness about occurrence of breast cancer

1= Individuals believe that breast cancer occurs at older age
 2= Individuals believes that breast cancer occurs at middle age

Figure 3: Awareness regarding effect of age occurrence of breast cancer

1= Individuals believe they know why breast cancer can occur

2= Individuals believes that cause of breast cancer is unknown

Figure 4: Awareness about causes of breast cancer

1= Individual believes smoking and drugs use induce breast cancer

2= individual believes that smoking and drugs use are note primary cause of breast cancer

Figure 5: Awareness about causes of cancer

1 = Individuals know about symptoms of breast cancer

2 = Individuals do not know about symptoms of breast cancer

Figure 6: Awareness regarding symptoms of breast cancer

1= Individuals know about mammography test
 2= Individuals do not know about mammography test

Figure 7: Awareness about mammography test

1= Individuals know about treatment of breast cancer
 2= Individuals do not know about treatment of breast cancer

Figure 8: Awareness regarding treatment of Breast Cancer

Table 1: Frequency distribution of major kinds of cancer in Hazara Division diagnosed during 2005 (Data collected from INOR, Abbottabad) Total Patients 927

Types of Cancer	% of Individuals	Types of Cancer	% of Individuals
CA BREAST	12	BRAIN TUMOR	5.6
GI TRACT TUMORS	9.9	HEMATOLOGICAL MALIGANANCIES	5.49
SKIN CANCER	8.5	ORAL CAVITY TUMORS	5
LYMPHOMAS	6.58	OVARIAN CANCER	4.85
HEPATOBIILIARY TUMORS	6.36	TOTAL PATIENT	927

Frequency distribution represented graphically of major kinds of cancer in Hazara Division diagnosed during 2005 data (collecting from INOR, Abbottabad)

Y-axis show the % age of the individuals.

Table 2: Frequency distribution of major kinds of cancer in Hazara Division diagnosed during 2006 (Data collected from INOR, Abbottabad) Total Patients 815

Types of Cancer	% of Individuals
BREAST CANCER	13.86
GI TRACT TUMORS	10.67
HEAD & NECK CANCERS	10.67
CNS TUMORS	9.08
SKIN CANCERS	7.36

Types of Cancer	% of Individuals
GYNEACOLOGICAL CANCER	6.26
LYMPHOMAS	5.88
HEMATOLOGICAL MALIGNANCIES	4.54
PROSTAE CANCER	3.44
LUNG CANCER	3.31

Frequency distribution represented graphically of major kinds of cancer in Hazara Division diagnosed during 2006 data (collecting from INOR, Abbottabad)

Y-axis show the %age of the individuals.

Table 3: Frequency distribution of major kinds of cancer in Hazara Division diagnosed during 2007 (Data collected from INOR, Abbottabad)

Types of Cancer	% of Individuals
BREAST CANCER	13.8
CNS TUMORS	10.26
GI TRACT TUMORS	10.03
SKIN CANCERS	9.46
HEAD & NECK CANCERS	8.66

Types of Cancer	% of Individuals
GYNEACOLOGICAL CANCER	7.64
LYMPHOMAS	6.04
HEMATOLOGICAL MALIGNANCIES	5.47
HEPATAOBILIARY TUMORS	4.22
LUNG CANCER	3.76

Frequency distribution represented graphically of major kinds of cancer in Hazara Division diagnosed during 2007 data (collecting from INOR, Abbottabad)

Y-axis show the %age of the individuals.

Table 4: Frequency distribution of major kinds of cancer in Hazara Division diagnosed during 2008 (Data collected from INOR, Abbottabad) Total Patients 802

Types of Cancer	% of Individuals
BREAST CANCER	11.2
GI TRACT TUMORS	9.2
CNS TUMORS	10.7
HEAD & NECK CANCERS	6.85
SKIN CANCERS	15.46

Types of Cancer	% of Individuals
GYNEACOLOGICAL CANCER	6.1
LYMPHOMAS	4.86
HEMATOLOGICAL MALIGNANCIES	5.6
HEPATAOBILIARY TUMORS	2.1
LUNG CANCER	2.49

Frequency distribution represented graphically of major kinds of cancer in Hazara Division diagnosed during 2008 data (collecting from INOR, Abbottabad) Y-axis show the %age of the individuals.

Conclusion

The findings in this study demonstrate that the prevalence rates of different cancer types in Northern Area of Pakistan show marked variation and these variations are highly statistically significant. Cancer poses an emerging and potentially significant health burden in Pakistan and it is expected that this burden will increase time to time due to rapidly growth and aging of the population. From the present study it has been concluded that there is heavy burden of cancer in Northern Area of Pakistan. Female are more affected than male. Most of the female are left undiagnosed and untreated due to their social, economic, religious and customary matters. There must be proper checkup of patients as healthy female contributes well in the society. Cancer registry institutes playing a major role in registration, diagnosing and treating cancer patients throughout Pakistan. An increased frequency of cancers of breast, lip and oral cavity, lung, non-Hodgkin lymphoma, colorectum, cervix uteri, esophagus and bladder are experienced in Pakistan. The burden of cancers can be prevented in affected areas to a larger extent by promoting knowledge related to cancer control, timely detection, vaccination and encouraging physical activity and healthy dietary patterns.

Additional studies from different regions of Pakistan need to be collected and analyzed to get a clearer picture of variation in cancer incidence and prevalence in Pakistan owing to the marked heterogeneity of ethnic types in different regions of the country.

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